

Supplementary Material for Point Cloud Segmentation with Guided Sampling and Continuous Interpolation

Appendix

A Derivation of Eq. (7) in the Main Paper

To interpolate the color \mathbf{f}_t of point t as depicted in Fig. 3b, let's interpolate along the vertical axis first:

$$\mathbf{f}_t = w_x \mathbf{f}_x + w_y \mathbf{f}_y, \quad (\text{a})$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{f}_x = w_q \mathbf{f}_q + w_s \mathbf{f}_s, \mathbf{f}_y = w_p \mathbf{f}_p + w_r \mathbf{f}_r. \quad (\text{b})$$

Substituting Eq. (b) into Eq. (a):

$$\mathbf{f}_t = w_x(w_q \mathbf{f}_q + w_s \mathbf{f}_s) + w_y(w_p \mathbf{f}_p + w_r \mathbf{f}_r) \quad (\text{c})$$

$$= w_x w_q \cdot \mathbf{f}_q + w_x w_s \cdot \mathbf{f}_s + w_y w_p \cdot \mathbf{f}_p + w_y w_r \cdot \mathbf{f}_r. \quad (\text{d})$$

Then, substituting Eq. (6) into Eq. (d):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}_t &= \frac{d(\mathbf{y}, t)}{d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} \cdot \frac{d(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})}{d(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{s})} \cdot \mathbf{f}_q + \frac{d(\mathbf{y}, t)}{d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} \cdot \frac{d(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{x})}{d(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{s})} \cdot \mathbf{f}_s \\ &\quad + \frac{d(\mathbf{x}, t)}{d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} \cdot \frac{d(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{y})}{d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{r})} \cdot \mathbf{f}_p + \frac{d(\mathbf{x}, t)}{d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} \cdot \frac{d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{y})}{d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{r})} \cdot \mathbf{f}_r. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{e})$$

Denoting A as the area of the grid formed by \mathbf{p} , \mathbf{q} , \mathbf{r} , and \mathbf{s} , and A_i as the area of the i -th rectangle marked in Fig. 3b, Eq. (e) is then:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}_t &= \frac{A_1}{A} \cdot \mathbf{f}_s + \frac{A_2}{A} \cdot \mathbf{f}_r + \frac{A_3}{A} \cdot \mathbf{f}_q + \frac{A_4}{A} \cdot \mathbf{f}_p \\ &= \frac{A_1 \mathbf{f}_s + A_2 \mathbf{f}_r + A_3 \mathbf{f}_q + A_4 \mathbf{f}_p}{A}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{f})$$

This shows that bilinear interpolation is the 2D grid equivalent of the barycentric interpolation method. \square

B Direct Use of Pointwise Features for Augmentation in the Spatial Domain

A direct method to integrate feature information into the farthest point sampling (FPS) process is by calculating distances within the feature-augmented point set in \mathbb{R}^{n+f}

Fig. A1: **Visualization of point sets sampled from a cylinder point cloud using different sampling spaces.** In this example, we use point normals as the point features $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{R}^f$, and visualize normal directions with colors. With the proposed DistrFPS, we manage to adaptively sample densely at the junction of the cylinder’s bases and side.

space. However, this method has limitations, as illustrated in Fig. A1. Here, a point cloud of a cylinder (with its normals as features) undergoes subsampling via FPS, employing distances derived from varying spaces. Crucially, boundaries demarcating homogeneous regions ought to be densely sampled to aid subsequent processing stages in accentuating these distinctive areas. For instance, the cylinder’s side and base manifest as distinct homogeneous regions. The conventional FPS (Fig. A1b) samples uniformly across all areas as it focuses on the point positions and not features. Although utilizing FPS within the \mathbb{R}^{n+f} space integrates feature details into the sampling, it neglects local feature nuances. Consequently, it barely introduces any significant variation (Fig. A1c). In contrast, DistrFPS (Fig. A1d) takes into account features from localized regions, ensuring denser sampling at the intersection of the cylinder’s base and side, and less frequent sampling elsewhere.

C Running Time

As detailed in the main paper, we follow established conventions to use a training and evaluation protocol that splits a input point cloud into subparts before processing, thereby enabling the neural network to operate independently of scene scale. On our hardware setup with a single NVIDIA 1080ti GPU, for an input point cloud comprising 50,000 points, sampling 12,500 points with FPS takes 102ms, and DistrFPS takes 128ms. Barycentric interpolation takes 762ms, where delaunay triangulation takes 223ms, finding enclosing the simplex of each point takes 121ms, and the actual interpolation process involves solving a linear system taking 418ms. With DistrFPS and barycentric interpolation equipped, training on fold-5 of S3DIS takes 55h, whereas the baseline which uses FPS with k -NN interpolation takes 35h.

Table A1: Network architectures.

Dataset	Task	Input	#neighbors	Strides	Feature dimensions	#blocks
S3DIS	semseg	$xyzRGB$	[8, 16, 16, 16, 16]	[1, 4, 4, 4, 4]	[32, 64, 128, 256, 512]	[1, 2, 3, 5, 2]
ScanNet	semseg	$xyzRGB$	[8, 16, 16, 16, 16]	[1, 4, 4, 4, 4]	[32, 64, 128, 256, 512]	[1, 2, 3, 5, 2]
ShapeNetPart	partseg	$xyzN_xN_yN_z$	[16, 32, 32, 32, 32]	[1, 4, 4, 4, 4]	[48, 96, 192, 384, 512]	[1, 2, 3, 5, 2]
ModelNet40	cls	$xyzN_xN_yN_z$	[8, 16, 16, 16, 16]	[1, 4, 4, 4, 4]	[32, 64, 128, 256, 512]	[1, 2, 3, 5, 2]

Table A2: Training configurations.

Dataset	Task	Backbone	Optimizer	Initial LR	Weight Decay	LR Scheduler	Total Epochs
S3DIS	semseg	PointTransformer	SGD	0.5	0.0001	MultiStep	800
S3DIS	semseg	PointNet++	AdamW	0.005	0.05	MultiStep	800
ScanNet	semseg	PointTransformer	AdamW	0.005	0.02	MultiStep	600
ShapeNetPart	partseg	PointTransformer	SGD	0.05	0.0001	MultiStep	200
ModelNet40	cls	PointTransformer	SGD	0.05	0.0001	MultiStep	100

D Experimental Setups

Network Architectures

We summarize the detailed network architectures in Tab. A1.

D.1 Training Configurations

We summarize our network training configurations in Tab. A2. Note that none of our experiments used loss balancing to boost test-time accuracy.

D.2 Semantic Segmentation on S3DIS

A 6-dimensional vector, comprised of a coordinate xyz and an RGB color vector, is used as input for each point. Before feeding the point cloud into the network, we grid-sample the input point cloud with a grid size of 0.04 meters following common practice [3, 8, 9, 15].

D.3 Semantic Segmentation on ScanNet

A 6-dimensional vector, comprised of a coordinate xyz and an RGB color vector, is used as input for each point. Before feeding the point cloud into the network, we grid-sample the input point cloud with a grid size of 0.02 meters.

D.4 Object Part Segmentation on ShapeNetPart

A 6-dimensional vector, comprised of a coordinate xyz and a normal vector $\mathbf{n} = (N_x, N_y, N_z)$, is used as input for each point. The data used in our experiments are

provided by [7] for a fair comparison with prior works. Following common practice [7, 9, 12, 13], we randomly sample 2,048 points from each object point cloud before it is fed into the network, and concatenate the one-hot encoding of the object’s shape category to the last layer of the network.

D.5 Shape Classification on ModelNet40

A 6-dimensional vector, comprised of a coordinate xyz and a normal vector \mathbf{n} , is used as input for each point. For our implementation of the FPS-based baseline [15] and the DistrFPS-based network used in Sec. 4.4 of the main paper, the sampling strategy of [6] is adopted where each shape is uniformly sampled to contain 2,048 points before it is fed into the network. The learned features generated by the encoder are average pooled to a single vector and fed to an MLP to obtain the final classification predictions.

E Metric Definitions

Table A3: **Metric definitions.** The MSE, PSNR, and SSIM metrics are calculated between two point sets $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_i\}$, $\mathcal{Y} = \{\mathbf{y}_i\}$, where $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$, and F denotes the largest possible value of the all of \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{y}_i . The mIoU, mAcc, and oAcc metrics reflect the segmentation accuracy according to each category c ’s number of true-positive (TP), false-positive (FP), true-negative (TN), and false-negative (FN) predictions.

Metric	Definition
MSE(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})	$\text{mean}_i(\ \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{y}_i\ _2)$
PSNR(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})	$20 \times \log_{10}(F/\text{MSE}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}))$
SSIM $_w(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})$	$\frac{(2\mu_{\mathcal{X}_w} \mu_{\mathcal{Y}_w} + C_1)(2\sigma_{\mathcal{X}_w \mathcal{Y}_w} + C_2)}{(\mu_{\mathcal{X}_w}^2 + \mu_{\mathcal{Y}_w}^2 + C_1)(\sigma_{\mathcal{X}_w}^2 + \sigma_{\mathcal{Y}_w}^2 + C_2)}$
SSIM(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})	$\text{mean}_{w \in \mathcal{V}} \text{SSIM}_w(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})$
mIoU	$\text{mean}_c \left(\frac{\text{TP}_c}{\text{TP}_c + \text{FP}_c + \text{FN}_c} \right)$
mAcc	$\text{mean}_c \left(\frac{\text{TP}_c}{\text{TP}_c + \text{FN}_c} \right)$
oAcc	$(\sum_c \text{TP}_c) / N$

We provide the definitions of the metrics for experiments on signal reconstruction segmentation, and classification in Tab. A3.

F Additional Results

This section includes detailed evaluation statistics and more visualizations of the segmentation experiments conducted in the main paper.

Fig. A2: Improvements upon the FPS+ k -NN baseline.

Table A4: Per-category IoU on the S3DIS [1] 6-fold benchmark.

Method	ceil.	floor	wall	beam	colu.	wind.	door	chair	table	book.	sofa	board	clut.
PointNet [6]	88.0	88.7	69.3	42.4	23.1	47.5	51.6	42.0	54.1	38.2	9.6	29.4	35.2
SPGraph [4]	89.9	95.1	76.4	62.8	47.1	55.3	68.4	73.5	69.2	63.2	45.9	8.7	52.9
PointCNN [5]	94.8	97.3	75.8	63.3	51.7	58.4	57.2	69.1	71.6	61.2	39.1	52.2	58.6
KPConv [10]	93.6	92.4	83.1	63.9	54.3	66.1	76.6	57.8	64.0	69.3	74.9	61.3	60.3
PointTransformer [15]	94.3	97.5	84.7	55.6	58.1	66.1	78.2	74.1	77.6	71.2	67.3	65.7	64.8
Ours	95.5	97.9	85.9	66.8	58.0	66.5	80.4	84.9	75.4	67.8	73.4	71.1	66.3

Table A5: Per-category IoU on the ShapeNetPart [14] dataset.

Method	inst. mIoU	aero.	bag	cap	car	chair	ear.	guit.	knif.	lamp	lapt.	moto.	mug	pist.	rock.	skat.	table
PointNet++ [7]	85.1	82.4	79.0	87.7	77.3	90.8	71.8	91.0	85.9	83.7	95.3	71.6	94.1	81.3	58.7	76.4	82.6
DGCNN [11]	85.1	84.0	83.4	86.7	77.8	90.6	74.7	91.2	87.5	82.8	95.7	66.3	94.9	81.1	63.5	74.5	82.6
PointCNN [5]	86.1	84.1	86.5	86.0	80.8	90.6	79.7	92.3	88.4	85.3	96.1	77.2	95.3	84.2	64.2	80.0	83.0
PointASNL [13]	86.1	84.1	84.7	87.9	79.7	92.2	73.7	91.0	87.2	84.2	95.8	74.4	95.2	81.0	63.0	76.3	83.2
RS-CNN [2]	86.2	82.7	86.4	84.1	78.2	90.4	69.3	91.4	87.0	83.5	95.4	66.0	92.6	81.8	56.1	75.8	82.2
KPConv [10]	86.4	84.6	86.3	87.2	81.1	91.1	77.8	92.6	88.4	82.7	96.2	78.1	95.8	85.4	69.0	82.0	83.6
Ours	86.7	85.4	83.2	86.7	81.3	91.9	78.4	92.1	88.9	86.0	96.1	74.6	95.1	83.9	59.7	77.1	83.5

F.1 Quantitative Results

We report per-category statistics for segmentation on S3DIS and ShapeNetPart in Tabs. A4 and A5.

F.2 Qualitative Results

We visualize the improvements upon the FPS+ k -NN baseline on the S3DIS 6-fold benchmark, where the improvements are the most significant.

G Why does FPS preform better than DistrFPS at low sampling ratios in Fig. 4?

DistrFPS favors regions with rapidly changing features, but the bulk of a meaningful signal is usually occupied by low-frequency regions. When the sampling ratio is too low, DistrFPS samples fewer points from these regions than FPS, causing poorer reconstruction quality.

References

1. Armeni, I., Sener, O., Zamir, A.R., Jiang, H., Brilakis, I., Fischer, M., Savarese, S.: 3d semantic parsing of large-scale indoor spaces. In: CVPR (2016) 6
2. Huang, Q., Wang, W., Neumann, U.: Recurrent slice networks for 3d segmentation of point clouds. In: CVPR (2018) 6

3. Lai, X., Liu, J., Jiang, L., Wang, L., Zhao, H., Liu, S., Qi, X., Jia, J.: Stratified transformer for 3d point cloud segmentation. In: CVPR (2022) [3](#)
4. Landrieu, L., Simonovsky, M.: Large-scale point cloud semantic segmentation with super-point graphs. In: CVPR (2018) [6](#)
5. Li, Y., Bu, R., Sun, M., Wu, W., Di, X., Chen, B.: PointCNN: Convolution on x-transformed points. In: NeurIPS (2018) [6](#)
6. Qi, C.R., Su, H., Mo, K., Guibas, L.J.: PointNet: Deep learning on point sets for 3d classification and segmentation. In: CVPR (2017) [4](#), [6](#)
7. Qi, C.R., Yi, L., Su, H., Guibas, L.J.: PointNet++: Deep hierarchical feature learning on point sets in a metric space. In: NeurIPS (2017) [4](#), [6](#)
8. Qian, G., Hammoud, H., Li, G., Thabet, A., Ghanem, B.: ASSANet: An Anisotropic Separable Set Abstraction for Efficient Point Cloud Representation Learning. In: NeurIPS (2021) [3](#)
9. Qian, G., Li, Y., Peng, H., Mai, J., Hammoud, H.A.A.K., Elhoseiny, M., Ghanem, B.: PointNeXt: Revisiting PointNet++ with improved training and scaling strategies. In: NeurIPS (2022) [3](#), [4](#)
10. Thomas, H., Qi, C.R., Deschaud, J.E., Marcotegui, B., Goulette, F., Guibas, L.: KPConv: Flexible and deformable convolution for point clouds. In: ICCV (2019) [6](#)
11. Wang, Y., Sun, Y., Liu, Z., Sarma, S.E., Bronstein, M.M., Solomon, J.M.: Dynamic graph cnn for learning on point clouds. TOG (2019) [6](#)
12. Xu, M., Ding, R., Zhao, H., Qi, X.: PACConv: Position Adaptive Convolution with Dynamic Kernel Assembling on Point Clouds. In: CVPR (2021) [4](#)
13. Yan, X., Zheng, C., Li, Z., Wang, S., Cui, S.: PointASNL: Robust point clouds processing using nonlocal neural networks with adaptive sampling. In: CVPR (2020) [4](#), [6](#)
14. Yi, L., Kim, V.G., Ceylan, D., Shen, I.C., Yan, M., Su, H., Lu, C., Huang, Q., Sheffer, A., Guibas, L.: A scalable active framework for region annotation in 3d shape collections. TOG (2016) [6](#)
15. Zhao, H., Jiang, L., Jia, J., Torr, P.H., Koltun, V.: Point transformer. In: ICCV (2021) [3](#), [4](#), [6](#)